

Privacy snapshot

Personal data is solely **collected** to the minimum necessary for each specific purpose of the processing.

Personal data is solely **retained** to the minimum necessary for each specific purpose of the processing.

Personal data is solely **processed** for the purposes it was provided for.

Personal data is solely **disseminated** to private third parties for purposes it was provided for and agreed upon.

No personal data is **sold**.

All personal data is retained in **encrypted** form.

